

NEW RECORDS OF PSOCOPTERA (INSECTA) FROM ALBANIA, BULGARIA AND SERBIA

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Abstract

The study presents new records of Psocoptera (Insecta) species from Albania, Bulgaria, and Serbia, enhancing the understanding of barkfly diversity in the Balkans. Noteworthy findings include the first records of *Hemineura dispar* Tetens, 1891 (species complex) from Albania, *Mesopsocus immunis* (Stephens, 1836) from Albania and Serbia, and *Amphigerontia intermedia* (Tetens, 1891) from Bulgaria. Additionally, *Ptycta nadleri* Galil, 1981, a species with limited distribution, was documented in Bulgaria, extending the known range of this species.

KEY WORDS: Barkflies, psocids, Balkans, species diversity.

Introduction

The exploration of barkfly (Insecta: Psocoptera) species diversity in the Balkans remains incomplete, requiring further comprehensive investigation. Following Lienhard's monograph (1998) covering Europe and the Mediterranean region, it became apparent that certain countries require targeted Psocoptera research efforts. Sziráki's contributions (Sziráki, 2013) expanded species records notably for Albania, Greece, the Republic of North Macedonia, and Serbia. Our short note supplements the Psocoptera checklists of Albania, Bulgaria, and Serbia with a few new records.

Material and Methods

The material was collected by a portable self-made automatic light trap with an 8 W 368 nm blacklight tube and funnel with a pot, powered by a 12 V portable battery. The specimens were stored in 96% ethanol, identified and deposited in the first author's collection. The photos (specimens in glycerin) were taken with a Canon PowerShot SX500IS through the eyepiece of an Optika light microscope. Taxonomy and species identification followed Lienhard (1998).

Results

Elipsocidae

***Hemineura dispar* Tetens, 1891** – species complex

Syn.: *H. fusca* Reuter, 1904

Material examined: Albania, Pogradec region, above Ohrid Lake, near Qafa Kotodeshit, N 41°02'33.4", E 20°36'10.8", 1,132 m a.s.l., 07.11.2023, 1 ♂, light trap, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova.

Remark: females are needed to identify species from the *dispar* complex (Lienhard, 1998). The species was known from many areas of Europe: Austria, Bulgaria, Cyprus, the Czech and Slovak Republics, Finland, France; Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, and Russia. No species from this genus have been recorded in Albania until now. (Lienhard, 2016; Sziráki, 2013).

Mesopsocidae

***Mesopsocus immunis* (Stephens, 1836)**

Syn.: *M. lusitanus* Lienhard, 1981; *M. unipunctatus* Kolbe, 1880

Material examined: Albania, Himara region, above Kudhes village, N 40°04'49.4", E 19°47'31.6", 376 m a.s.l., 25.05.2023, 1 ♂, light trap, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova; Serbia, Svrljiške planine Mts, above Moklište village, N 43°16'39.0", E 22°17'50.0", 700 m a.s.l., 29.06.2020, 1 ♂, light trap, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova.

Remark: New record for Albania and Serbia. The species was known from many areas of Europe (including Bulgaria) and some localities in North Africa (Morocco) and North America (Canada) (Lienhard, 2016).

Psocidae

***Amphigerontia intermedia* (Tetens, 1891)**

Material examined: Bulgaria, Upper Thracian Lowland, Bozduganovska Koriya forest, *Quercus* sp., *Fraxinus* sp. and *Carpinus betulus* forest, N 42°22'17.9", E 25°44'30.0", 126 m a.s.l., 28.05.2022, 1 ♂, from *Prunus spinosa*, collected by beating the vegetation, leg. D. Georgiev.

Remark: New record for Bulgaria. The species was known from Germany, the Czech Republic, Finland, France, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, the Slovak Republic, Sweden, Switzerland, and Russia (Lienhard, 2016).

***Ptycta nadleri* Galil, 1981**

Material examined: Bulgaria, South Black Sea coast, Atanasovsko Lake near the Chernomore mine, bush area, N 42°34'41.9", E 27°29'41.9", 11 m a.s.l., 05.09.2022, 1 ♀ (Fig. 1), light trap, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova.

Remark: This species, with a relatively unknown distribution, was initially described by Galil (1981) from Israel and later redescribed by Lienhard (1986) based on paratypes from Israel (Jerusalem) and newly collected specimens from Romania (Agigea, North Black Sea coast). The Bulgarian locality lies between these two locations, approximately 200 km in a straight line from the Romanian site and 1,400 km from the type locality.

Figure 1. *Ptycta nadleri* Galil, 1981 (female) from the Bulgarian South Black Sea coast, lateral and ventral view of the collected specimen (antennae lacking).

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НОВИ ПОДАЦИ ЗА PSOCOPTERA (INSECTA) ИЗ АЛБАНИЈЕ, БУГАРСКЕ И СРБИЈЕ

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Извод

Објављени су нови подаци о врстама Psocoptera (Insecta) из Албаније, Бугарске и Србије, што представља допринос разумевању диверзитета на Балкану. Значајни налази укључују прве податке о *Hemineura dispar* Tetens, 1891 (комплекс врста) из Албаније, *Mesopsocus immunis* (Stephens, 1836) из Албаније и Србије и *Amphigerontia intermedia* (Tetens, 1891) из Бугарске. Поред тога, *Ptycta nadleri* Galil, 1981 врста са ограниченом распрострањеношћу, забележена је у Бугарској.

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